

REVIEW ARTICLE

EXPLORING SUPERDISINTEGRANTS FOR FAST- DISSOLVING ORAL FORMULATIONS: FOCUS ON TYPES, MECHANISMS AND MARKET INSIGHTS

Pandian. C*, Punniyamoorthy. K, Sudhir V.V, Navina. S and Praveenrajan A.K

Department of Pharmaceutics, College of Pharmacy, Madurai Medical College, The Tamil Nadu Dr. M.G.R. Medical University affiliated College, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

*Corresponding author E-mail: drcpandian73@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16410507>

Abstract:

Superdisintegrating polymers play a pivotal role in the development of modern oral drug delivery systems, particularly in formulations designed for rapid onset of action and improved patient compliance. These polymers are excipients that enable the tablet to break down quickly into smaller fragments upon contact with saliva or gastrointestinal fluids, enhancing the dissolution, bioavailability and absorption of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API). They are especially critical in the formulation of oral disintegrating tablets (ODTs), fast-dissolving films, and chewable dosage forms. ODTs are solid dosage forms containing medicinal substances which disintegrate rapidly, usually in a matter of seconds, when placed on the tongue. The mechanism by which disintegrating polymer function involves various physicochemical processes, including swelling, wicking (capillary action), chemical gas formation, and enzymatic degradation. These actions facilitate rapid tablet disintegration without the need for water, making them ideal for pediatric, geriatric, and dysphagic patients. Disintegrating polymers are widely used in the treatment of various conditions such as motion sickness, nausea, schizophrenia, epilepsy, allergies, and pain management, where fast therapeutic action is essential. Both natural (e.g., starch, guar gum) and synthetic (e.g., croscopovidone, croscarmellose sodium) polymers are utilized, with ongoing research focusing on novel, biodegradable, and plant-based alternatives to improve performance and safety. The aim of this article is to review various super disintegrating polymers, its mechanism of action, application of such polymers in various diseases.

Keyword: Super Disintegrating Polymers, Rapid Tablet Disintegration, Rapid Onset of Action, Bioavailability.

Introduction:

Super disintegrating polymers are water-soluble or water-swellaable polymers used in drug delivery systems, particularly in orally disintegrating films (ODFs) and tablets, to enable rapid dissolution or disintegration in the oral cavity, often within seconds, without the need for water or chewing. These polymers facilitate the quick release of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) upon contact with saliva. The oral route remains the most preferred method for drug administration due to its numerous advantages over other routes of delivery.^[1] Patients who are unconscious, elderly, or very young, suffer from conditions that make swallowing or chewing difficult. These dosage forms are designed to disintegrate and dissolve in the oral cavity without the need for water and when they are placed on the tongue or oral mucosa, where they quickly become moistened by saliva and disintegrate, allowing for rapid drug release and absorption either through the oral mucosa or gastrointestinal tract. Natural and synthetic super disintegrants both have better effects on rapid dissolving oral thin films, usually they are used when the drug is poorly water soluble, poor gel formation, to increase the good hydration capacity, and complexation.^[2]

Disintegration

Disintegration refers to the mechanical breakdown of a compressed tablet into smaller granules after ingestion. This process involves the disruption of the interparticle bonds formed during the tablet compaction stage. Disintegration also includes the interaction between the tablet and bodily fluids such as saliva and gastric fluids. For effective disintegration to occur, the disintegrant within the tablet must rapidly absorb saliva, causing it to swell. This swelling leads to volume expansion and the generation of hydrostatic pressure, which collectively help to break the tablet apart quickly, often starting in the mouth. This rapid breakdown is essential for ensuring timely drug release and absorption.^[3]

Disintegrants

Disintegrants are substances incorporated into tablets and some capsule formulations to facilitate their breakdown into smaller particles when they come into contact with an aqueous environment. This disintegration process is essential as it increases the surface area available for drug release, thereby promoting faster and more efficient absorption of the active pharmaceutical ingredient. The primary function of disintegrants is to break down the tablet matrix, enhance moisture penetration, and promote the dispersion of the tablet components. This ensures that the drug is released quickly and can begin to act promptly within the body. Common disintegrants used in pharmaceutical formulations include natural starches such as maize and corn starch, partially pregelatinized starch, and low substituted hydroxypropyl cellulose.^[4] Other substances like clays, gums, resins, and finely divided microcrystalline cellulose can also serve as effective disintegrants. These materials play a critical role in ensuring the proper performance of oral solid dosage forms by supporting rapid tablet disintegration and drug release.

Superdisintegrants

A new class of disintegrants known as super disintegrants has been developed. These substances are more effective than traditional disintegrants, as they act more rapidly and require lower concentrations to achieve the desired effect. Super disintegrants possess specific physical and functional

properties, including a pleasing appearance and enhanced performance tailored to pharmaceutical needs. Unlike conventional disintegrants that absorb significant amounts of water, super disintegrants are derived from modified super-absorbing materials and are designed to swell rapidly upon exposure to fluids rather than absorb them extensively. Their primary mechanism involves rapid swelling and structural weakening, which facilitates the quick breakup of tablets into primary particles.^[6] This accelerates the dissolution or release of the active pharmaceutical ingredients. Additionally, super disintegrants enhance moisture penetration and promote the dispersion of the tablet matrix. Their main function is to overcome the binding forces and compression stresses that give the tablet its structure, thereby ensuring efficient disintegration and improved drug bioavailability.^[3,5]

Criteria for Choosing Superdisintegrants^[7-9]

The selection of super disintegrants plays a vital role in determining the disintegration rate of tablets, directly impacting the effectiveness and onset of drug action. However, beyond promoting rapid disintegration, super disintegrants can influence other important tablet characteristics such as hardness, mouthfeel, and friability, especially when used in higher concentrations. Therefore, careful consideration must be given when choosing a super disintegrant for a specific formulation. Several key factors should guide this selection process.

Here are the criteria for selecting super disintegrants presented as detailed points:

1. Rapid Disintegration

- The super disintegrant should enable the tablet to break apart quickly upon contact with saliva or gastrointestinal fluids.
- This ensures fast release and absorption of the active pharmaceutical ingredient.

2. Tablet Hardness and Friability

- The selected super disintegrant should help produce tablets that are sufficiently hard to withstand handling and packaging.
- It should minimize friability (tendency to crumble), maintaining tablet integrity during processing and storage.

3. Pleasant Mouthfeel

- Super disintegrants should not leave a gritty or unpleasant sensation in the mouth.
- A small particle size is preferred to ensure a smooth texture and enhance patient acceptability, especially for orally disintegrating tablets.

4. Good Flow Characteristics

- The super disintegrant should exhibit good powder flow properties.
- This improves the overall flowability of the tablet blend, aiding in uniform tablet production and reducing manufacturing issues.

Ideal Properties of Superdisintegrants^[10]

1. Excellent Compressibility and Flowability

Superdisintegrants must possess good flow and compressibility characteristics to ensure uniform tablet formation. Powders demonstrating a compressibility index between 12% and 16% are

generally considered to exhibit good flow. Among various superdisintegrants, crospovidone shows superior compressibility when compared to others.

2. Low Solubility

The solubility of excipients significantly affects the rate and mechanism of tablet disintegration. Water-soluble substances tend to dissolve rather than disintegrate, while insoluble excipients promote quicker tablet breakdown, making them more suitable for fast-dissolving formulations.

3. Limited Gel Formation

Gelling behavior can impede drug release, as the active ingredient must diffuse through the gel matrix. To avoid this, superdisintegrants with minimal gel-forming potential are preferred. For example, Primojel, when used at concentrations between 4–6%, demonstrates effective disintegration without substantial gel formation.

4. High Hydration Capacity

The hydration ability of a superdisintegrant influences its effectiveness, particularly in formulations containing hydrophobic drugs or excipients that may adsorb onto the disintegrant surface. Utilizing disintegrants with a high water uptake capacity can enhance wetting and promote better disintegration and dissolution.

5. Minimal Drug-Excipient Complexation

Certain anionic disintegrants, such as croscarmellose sodium and Primojel, can form complexes with positively charged drug molecules, potentially slowing their release. In contrast, crospovidone, a non-ionic polymer, avoids such interactions, facilitating a more consistent drug release.

Advantages of Superdisintegrants ^[11]

1. **Remarkable tendency on wetting causing rapid disintegration:** Superdisintegrants absorb water quickly, swell, and help the tablet break apart rapidly upon contact with moisture.
2. **No lump formation on disintegration:** Efficient disintegration occurs uniformly without forming clumps, which ensures better drug dissolution and absorption.
3. **Compatible with commonly used therapeutic agents and excipients:** Chemical compatibility with active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) and other excipients ensures stability and efficacy.
4. **Does not stick to the punches and dies:** Prevents manufacturing issues like sticking during tablet compression, ensuring smooth production and consistent quality.
5. **Effective in lower concentrations:** Only a small amount (often 2–8% w/w) is needed, which minimizes formulation cost and space constraints in the tablet matrix.
6. **Less effect on compressibility and flowability:** Does not significantly interfere with the tablet's mechanical strength or the flow of the powder blend, aiding in consistent tablet formation.
7. **More effective intragranularly:** When incorporated inside granules (intragranularly), it can still effectively contribute to disintegration, sometimes even more so than extragranular use.
8. **Some are anionic and may cause some slight in vitro binding with cationic drugs:** Electrostatic interactions between anionic superdisintegrants and cationic drugs can affect drug release, needing evaluation during formulation.

- 9. Biodegradable:** Environmentally friendly and safe for biological systems, aligning with sustainability and safety considerations.

Disadvantages ^[12-13]

- 1. High-Dose Drugs:** Incorporating drugs that require high doses into films is challenging due to the limited capacity of the film matrix to accommodate large amounts of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). Typically, ODFs contain 5–30% w/w of the API, making them suitable for low-dose medications.
- 2. Dosage Uniformity:** Achieving consistent dosage across each film can be difficult, especially when APIs have varying solubility profiles or interact differently with film-forming polymers.
- 3. Moisture Sensitivity:** ODFs are susceptible to moisture, which can lead to degradation of the film and the API. This necessitates the use of moisture-resistant packaging and careful storage conditions.
- 4. Special Packaging Requirements:** To maintain stability and prevent moisture absorption, ODFs often require specialized packaging, such as foil pouches with desiccants.
- 5. pH Sensitivity of APIs:** APIs that are unstable at the pH of saliva (approximately 6.8) cannot be effectively formulated into ODFs, as they may degrade before reaching systemic circulation.
- 6. Oral Mucosal Irritation:** Certain APIs or excipients may cause irritation to the oral mucosa, limiting their suitability for ODF formulations.

How Superdisintegrants Act? ^[14-16]

1. Swelling

Swelling is a primary mechanism where disintegrant particles absorb water and expand in all directions, creating internal pressure that disrupts the tablet matrix. This expansion overcomes the adhesive forces between the tablet components, leading to disintegration. For instance, starch-based disintegrants like sodium starch glycolate and croscarmellose sodium exhibit significant swelling upon hydration.

However, tablet porosity plays a crucial role in swelling efficiency. High porosity can reduce the swelling pressure, while low porosity can impede liquid penetration, both affecting disintegration performance.

2. Wicking (Capillary Action)

Wicking involves the movement of water into the tablet through capillary action, facilitated by the disintegrant's hydrophilic properties. Materials like crospovidone and croscarmellose sodium enhance tablet porosity, allowing rapid fluid penetration. As water enters, it weakens the interparticulate bonds, leading to tablet disintegration.

3. Deformation Recovery

Some disintegrants, such as potato starch, undergo plastic deformation during tablet compression. Upon contact with water, these particles recover their original shape, generating internal pressure that contributes to disintegration. This mechanism is particularly effective under high compaction pressures.

4. Other Mechanisms

- **Heat of Wetting:** Certain disintegrants release heat upon hydration, causing localized expansion and aiding disintegration. This mechanism is less commonly utilized in modern formulations.
- **Particle Repulsion:** Electrostatic repulsive forces between similarly charged particles can contribute to disintegration, although this effect is secondary to water absorption.
- **Gas Release:** Effervescent tablets utilize the reaction between acids and bases (e.g., citric acid and sodium bicarbonate) to release carbon dioxide gas, creating internal pressure that causes the tablet to disintegrate.
- **Enzymatic Action:** Enzymes present in the gastrointestinal tract can degrade specific excipients, facilitating tablet disintegration.

Fig. 1: Mechanism of action of superdisintegrants ^[17]

The above figure explains the mechanism of action of superdisintegrants in a tablet.

(a) swelling, (b) wicking, and (c) strain recovery mechanisms.

Types of Superdisintegrants ^[20]

1. Natural superdisintegrants
2. Synthetic superdisintegrants
3. Co-processed superdisintegrants

1. Natural superdisintegrants ^[18-22]

Ispaghula Husk Mucilage (*Plantago ovata*)

Ispaghula husk, derived from the dried seeds of *Plantago ovata*, contains mucilage located in the seed epidermis. The mucilage is extracted by soaking the seeds in distilled water for 48 hours followed by brief boiling, filtration, and precipitation using acetone. Upon drying below 60°C, the

mucilage exhibits remarkable pharmaceutical potential due to its high swelling index ($\sim 89 \pm 2.2\%$ v/v), making it a highly effective natural superdisintegrant. Compared to synthetic agents like crospovidone, *Plantago ovata* mucilage demonstrates faster tablet disintegration and is particularly beneficial in the formulation of fast-dissolving tablets due to its combined binding, disintegrating, and sustaining properties.

Locust Bean Gum

Locust bean gum has been identified for its bioadhesive properties and ability to enhance solubility, making it a promising candidate for pharmaceutical and biotechnological applications. Its functionality at various concentrations supports its role as a natural disintegrating polymer in oral dosage forms.

Mango Peel Pectin

Pectin extracted from dried mango peel, which is a significant byproduct of mango processing (20–25%), demonstrates a high swelling index and excellent solubility in physiological fluids. These characteristics make it suitable for use in fast-dispersing tablets, offering a sustainable and effective natural disintegrant.

Soy Polysaccharide

Soy polysaccharide, a starch- and sugar-free natural superdisintegrant, is particularly valuable in nutritional and health-related formulations. It shows disintegration performance comparable to synthetic agents like cross-linked sodium carboxymethyl cellulose and corn starch, especially in direct compression tablet formulations.

Xanthan Gum

Xanthan gum, a microbial polysaccharide produced by *Xanthomonas campestris*, is recognized in the USP. It is characterized by high hydrophilicity and extensive swelling capacity despite its low solubility and minimal gelling tendency, making it suitable for promoting rapid tablet disintegration.

Gellan Gum

Gellan gum, obtained from *Pseudomonas elodea*, is a linear anionic polysaccharide that swells rapidly upon hydration. Its hydrophilic nature enables swift tablet disintegration, with complete disintegration observed within 4 minutes at 4% w/w concentration, highlighting its efficacy as a superdisintegrant.

Chitin/Chitosan–Silicon Dioxide Complex

Chitin, sourced from marine shell waste, is converted to chitosan via deacetylation. When coprecipitated with silicon dioxide, the resulting complex outperforms conventional disintegrants. Studies have shown that tablets containing chitin disintegrate within 5–10 minutes regardless of the drug's solubility. Chitosan is widely utilized in pharmaceutical applications due to its multifunctionality and biocompatibility.

The following table discusses about various Natural Superdisintegrants and drug release profiles based in disintegration time.

Table 1: Natural Superdisintegrants And Drug Release Profiles ^[21]

S. No	Plant mucilage	Drug	Result
1.	<i>Plantago ovata</i> mucilage	Prochlorperazine maleate	Dispersion time within 8 seconds. At Concentration of 8% w/w.
2.	Fenugreek seed mucilage	Metformin hydrochloride	It shows 15.6 sec disintegration time and 100% drug release within 18 minutes at concentration of 4% w/w.
3.	<i>Lepidium sativum</i>	Nimesulide	Disintegration time of 17 sec and mean dissolution time 5.27 sec. at 10% w/w concentration, found better than other synthetic disintegration like Ac-di-sol and SSG.
4.	<i>Hibiscus rosa - sinensis</i> Linn. Mucilage powder.	Aceclofenac	At concentration of 6% w/w showed disintegration time of 20 sec.
5.	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> mucilage powder and seed powder	Metformin hydrochloride	At 5%w/w concentration, mucilage powder and seed powder both at disintegrated in 43 sec. and 45 sec. respectively
6.	Chitosan	Cinnarizine	Good mouth feels and disintegration time of 60 sec. at the level of 3% w/w.

2. Synthetic superdisintegrants ^[23-27]

Modified Starch (Sodium Starch Glycolate, Primojel)

Sodium starch glycolate is the sodium salt of carboxymethyl ether of starch, obtained through chemical modification and crosslinking, typically of potato starch, to enhance disintegration performance. The extent of crosslinking and substitution significantly influences its efficiency as a superdisintegrant. While native starches swell only 10–20% in water, modified starches can expand up to 200–300%, enabling rapid tablet disintegration—often in under two minutes. This rapid disintegration is driven by fast water uptake and a consequent dramatic increase in particle volume.

Cross-linked Polyvinylpyrrolidone (Crospovidone)

Crospovidone is a synthetic, highly porous polymer that rapidly absorbs saliva and swells, generating hydrostatic pressure for fast disintegration, especially suitable for orally disintegrating tablets. Scanning electron microscopy reveals a highly porous and granular structure, which supports excellent liquid wicking. Unlike sodium starch glycolate or croscarmellose sodium, crospovidone does not form a gel upon hydration, maintaining its rapid disintegration properties even at higher concentrations. Used at 2–5% levels in direct compression or granulation, it also offers excellent compressibility and provides a smooth mouthfeel due to its small particle size.

Modified Celluloses (Croscarmellose Sodium)

Croscarmellose sodium, a cross-linked derivative of sodium carboxymethylcellulose, is an insoluble, free-flowing powder with superior swelling and absorption properties. It can swell 4–8 times its volume, with a swelling index of approximately $65 \pm 1.7\%$ v/v. This superdisintegrant offers excellent water-wicking and swelling capacity, accelerating drug release and tablet breakdown. It is effective at low concentrations (0.5–2.0%) and can be used in both direct compression and wet granulation. For optimal performance in wet granulation, it is recommended to be incorporated intra- and extra-granularly.

Microcrystalline Cellulose (Avicel)

Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) is a partially depolymerized, purified cellulose appearing as a white, odorless, crystalline powder composed of porous particles. When used in concentrations below 10%, MCC significantly enhances tablet disintegration through a wicking mechanism—drawing water into the tablet matrix via capillary pores, which leads to the disruption of hydrogen bonds between cellulose microcrystals. This rapid water uptake initiates tablet breakup. In oral disintegrating tablets (ODTs), high MCC concentrations may cause adherence to the tongue due to rapid surface dehydration. Its high water wicking ability, especially in combination with starch, makes it highly effective for formulating fast-disintegrating tablets. Commercial grades like Avicel PH-101, PH-102, and PH-105 are available with variations in particle size and moisture content for tailored pharmaceutical applications.

Alginates

Alginates are naturally derived hydrophilic colloidal substances extracted from brown seaweeds, or synthetically modified from alginic acid or its salts. Composed of alternating units of D-mannuronic acid and L-glucuronic acid, alginates exhibit excellent water affinity and high swelling capacity. These features make alginic acid and sodium alginate effective disintegrants in tablet formulations. Alginic acid is typically used at 1–5%, while sodium alginate is effective in the 2.5–10% concentration range. They are particularly beneficial in formulations containing ascorbic acid and multivitamins, contributing to both disintegration and matrix stability.

The following table discusses about various Synthetic Superdisintegrants and drug release profiles based in disintegration time.

Table 2: Synthetic Superdisintegrants and Drug Release Profiles ^[27]

SL No	Synthetic Super disintegrants	Properties	Concentration and mechanism of disintegration	Drug used
1.	Croscarmellose Sodium	It is insoluble in water, although it rapidly swells to 4 – 8 times its original volume on contact with water. 0.81 – 0.83 m ² /g is the specific area and swelling index is 65±1.7% v/v.	It may be used in the range of 2%w/w. Fast absorption of water followed by rapid swelling. <i>The drug levocetirizine with 2% croscarmellose sodium show disintegration time of 15 sec and drug release was 96.80%.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fenofibrate • Donepezil hydrochloride • Lovastatin • Levocetirizine
2.	Sodium starch glycolate	Rapid absorption causes swelling of up to 6%. Rise in concentration causes gelling and loss of disintegration and Swelling index 52±1.2% v/v.	It is used in the limit of 2-8%w/w. Fast water uptake followed by speed swelling. Above 8%, disintegration times may actually increase due to gelling and its subsequent viscosity producing effects. The drug Loperamide having 6% SSG as super disintegrants with 0.2ml PG and HPMC-E50 as polymer show disintegration time of 3.48sec, drug content uniformity was 99.04% and dissolution study was found to be 99.4%.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fenofibrate • Donepezil hydrochloride • Loperamide
3.	Crospovidone	It is absolutely insoluble in water. Rapidly disperses and swell in water. Increase in the rate of swelling compared to other disintegrants. Large surface level to volume ratio than other disintegrants. Swelling index 58±1.5% v/v.	It is used in the range of 2-5% w/w. combination of swelling and wicking. Least disintegration time of 10.33 sec, and more than 90% drug release with in 5min was seen for the film containing drug as donepezil hydro-chloride polymer sodium alginate and cross povidone as super disintegrants compared to (CCS, SSG). The drug lovastatin with 4% Crospovidone as super disintegrants show disintegration time of 7sec, drug content uniformity was 98.86% and dissolution study was found to be 99.27%.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Donepezil hydrochloride • Lovastatin
4.	Polacrillin potassium	No lumps formation after disintegration. Eye compatibility with excipients and common therapeutics.	It is used in range of 0.5-5%w/w. Quick water uptake followed by rapid swelling and as a taste masking agent for various drugs.	

3. Co-processed Superdisintegrants ^[28]

Co-processed superdisintegrants represent a significant advancement in pharmaceutical excipient technology. Unlike traditional single-component superdisintegrants, co-processed superdisintegrants are formulated by blending two or more excipients that are specifically chosen and engineered to function synergistically. The goal of this combination is to leverage the strengths of each individual component while minimizing their individual limitations. This results in a more efficient and effective disintegrant. Co-processed superdisintegrants offer enhanced tablet performance, particularly in promoting rapid disintegration, improving dissolution, and increasing the bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs. Their unique design allows for improved functionality and consistency, making them highly beneficial in the formulation of modern solid oral dosage forms.

The following table discusses about various Co-processed superdisintegrants and its composition.

Table 3: List of Co-Processed Superdisintegrants ^[29,40]

S. No.	Co-Processed Superdisintegrants	Consist of
1	Ludipress	Lactose monohydrate (93%), Kollidon 30 (3.5%) and Kollidon CL (3.5%).
2	Ludiflash	D-mannitol 82.0-92.0%, Kollidon 4.0-6.0%, CL SF, 3.5-6.0% Polyvinyl acetate, 0.5-2.0% water and 0.25-0.60% Povidone.
3	Starlac	Lactose and starch
4	Starlac 1500	Alpha-lactose-monohydrate 85% and white maize starch 15%
5	Ran-Explo-S	Microcrystalline cellulose, silica and sodium starch glycolate ³

The manufacturing process of co-processed superdisintegrants involves the use of advanced techniques such as spray drying, co-grinding, and co-precipitation. These methods enable precise control over both the composition and physical structure (morphology) of the resulting product. Such control ensures that the final co-processed superdisintegrant exhibits optimized performance characteristics, such as improved flow, compressibility, and disintegration efficiency. Additionally, these techniques facilitate the systematic optimization and characterization of the material, allowing formulators to customize the excipient to meet specific formulation needs. As a result, co-processed superdisintegrants offer a versatile and adaptable solution in the development of advanced drug delivery systems, particularly where rapid disintegration and enhanced bioavailability are desired.

List of Marketed Products

Table 4: List Of Oral Disintegrating Tablets ^[30,39]

Trade Name	Active Drug	Manufacturer
Felden fast melt	Piroxicam	Pfizer
Ugesic	Piroxicam	Mayer organic
Esulide MD	Nimesulide	Doff Biotech
Kazoldil MD	Nimesulide	Kaizen drugs
Mosid MD	Mosapride	Torrent Pharma
Valus	Valdecoxib	Glenmark
Vomidon MD	Domperidone	Olcare lab
Claritin redi Tab	Loratidine	Schering Plough
Maxalt MLT	Rizatriptan	Merck and Co
Zyprexa	Olanzapine	Eli Lilly

Table 5: List of Oral Disintegrating Films ^[31,41]

Trade Name	Active Drug	Manufacturer
Listerine	Cool mint	Pfizer
Triaminic	Dextromethorphan HBr	Novartis
Donepezil Rapid Film	Donepezil	Labtec
Sudafed PE	Phenylephrine	Wolters Kluwer
Suppress	Menthol	Innozen
Chloraseptic	Benzocaine menthol	Prestige
Gas-X	Simethicone	Novartis
Theraflu	Dextromethorphan HBr	Novartis
Setofilm	Ondansetron	BioalliancePharma
Zuplenz	Ondansetron	MonoSol Rx

Applications

Superdisintegrants are crucial excipients in pharmaceutical formulations, enhancing the disintegration and dissolution of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). Their application spans various dosage forms, improving bioavailability and patient compliance. Here's an overview of their applications:

1. Immediate-Release Tablets ^[32]

Superdisintegrants like croscarmellose sodium, crospovidone, and sodium starch glycolate are incorporated into immediate-release tablet formulations to facilitate rapid disintegration and dissolution of the API. This ensures quick onset of action and enhances therapeutic efficacy. For instance, a study on salbutamol sulphate ODTs demonstrated that formulations with croscarmellose sodium and sodium

starch glycolate disintegrated in approximately 19.28 seconds, highlighting their effectiveness in rapid drug release.

2. Orally Disintegrating Tablets (ODTs) ^[33]

ODTs are designed to disintegrate rapidly in the mouth, eliminating the need for water. Superdisintegrants such as croscarmellose sodium and crospovidone are essential in these formulations, ensuring quick disintegration and drug release. Their use is particularly beneficial for patients with dysphagia or those requiring rapid onset of action.

3. Effervescent Tablets ^[34]

Effervescent tablets, which release carbon dioxide upon contact with water, benefit from the inclusion of superdisintegrants. These excipients enhance the disintegration efficiency, ensuring rapid drug release and uniform dispersion of the API in the dissolution medium. This is particularly advantageous for drugs with poor solubility or bioavailability.

4. Granules and Pellets ^[35]

In granules and pellets, superdisintegrants improve disintegration and dissolution properties. They promote uniform dispersion of drug particles within the matrix, leading to faster drug release and absorption upon administration. This is beneficial for modified-release formulations and taste-masking applications.

5. Capsules ^[36]

Superdisintegrants are incorporated into capsule formulations to enhance the dissolution and bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs.

6. Lyophilized Formulations ^[37]

In lyophilized formulations, superdisintegrants improve reconstitution and dissolution properties. They enhance the rapid rehydration of lyophilized cakes upon addition of the reconstitution fluid, ensuring quick dispersion and dissolution of the drug substance. This is particularly important for biologics and injectable drugs, maintaining therapeutic effectiveness and patient safety.

7. Topical Formulations ^[38]

Superdisintegrants are utilized in topical formulations such as creams, ointments, and gels to enhance drug release and skin permeation. They improve the dispersion of the drug substance within the formulation matrix, promoting its release onto the skin surface and facilitating transdermal absorption. This allows for localized drug delivery and targeted therapy, minimizing systemic side effects.

Conclusion:

The evolution of disintegrants from natural substances to synthetic superdisintegrants has significantly advanced pharmaceutical formulations, enhancing drug bioavailability and patient compliance. Natural disintegrants, such as starch and cellulose derivatives, laid the foundation for tablet disintegration. The advent of synthetic superdisintegrants like croscarmellose sodium, crospovidone, and sodium starch glycolate has revolutionized tablet design, offering rapid disintegration and improved dissolution rates. Currently, the pharmaceutical industry is witnessing a shift towards incorporating natural and co-processed superdisintegrants, driven by the demand for sustainable and biocompatible

excipients. These natural alternatives offer advantages such as biodegradability and reduced toxicity, aligning with the growing emphasis on green chemistry and environmental sustainability in drug development. Looking ahead, the future of disintegrants and superdisintegrants lies in the integration of advanced technologies, including nanotechnology and 3D printing, to create personalized and controlled-release dosage forms. Furthermore, the development of multifunctional excipients that not only aid in disintegration but also enhance drug stability and targeting will be pivotal in the next generation of pharmaceutical formulations. The strategic selection and innovative application of disintegrants and superdisintegrants are crucial in the design of effective and patient-friendly oral dosage forms. Continued research and development in this field are essential to meet the evolving therapeutic needs and to ensure the delivery of safe and efficacious medications.

References:

1. Ansel, H. C., Popvich, N. G., & Allen, L. V. (1998). *Pharmaceutical dosage forms and drug delivery system* (1st ed., p. 78).
2. Jain, N. K., & Sharma, S. N. (1998). *A textbook of professional pharmacy* (4th ed., pp. 16–25).
3. Lachman, L., & Liberman, H. A. (1990). *Theory and practice of industrial pharmacy* (3rd ed., pp. 293–299).
4. Sastry, S. V., Nyshadham, J. R., & Fix, J. A. (2000). Recent technological advances in oral drug delivery – a review. *Pharmaceutical Science and Technology Today*, 3(4), 138–145.
5. Shukla, D., Chakraborty, S., Singh, S., & Mishra, B. (2009). Mouth dissolving tablets: An overview of formulation technology. *Scientia Pharmaceutica*, 77(2), 309–326.
6. Bhyan, B., Jangra, S., Kaur, M., & Singh, H. (2011). Orally fast dissolving films: Innovations in formulation and technology. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, 9(2), 50–57.
7. Dhiman, J., et al. (2022). Superdisintegrants – A brief review. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 12(1), 170–175.
8. Pathare, Y. S., Hastak, V. S., & Bajaj, A. N. (2013). Polymers used for fast disintegrating oral films: A review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, 21(1), 169–178.
9. Arya, A., & Chandra, A. (2010). Fast dissolving oral films: An innovative drug delivery system and dosage form. *International Journal of ChemTech Research*, 2, 576–583.
10. Dhere, P., & Patwekar, S. (2011). Review on preparation and evaluation of oral disintegrating films. *International Journal of Pharmacy & Technology*, 3, 1572–1585.
11. Thakur, R., & Narwal, S. (2012). Orally disintegrating preparations: Recent advancement in formulation and technology. *Journal of Drug Delivery & Therapeutics*, 2, 87–96.
12. Kaur, R., Bala, R., & Malik, D. (2012). A novel approach in oral fast dissolving drug delivery system – A review. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Technology and Research*, 2, 88–104.
13. Radhakisan, U., Chauhan, V., & Tribhuvan, N. (2012). Mouth dissolving film and their patent: An overview. *International Research Journal of Pharmacy*, 3, 39–42.

14. Patel, K., Soni, S., Patel, R., Pandya, V., & Bharadia, P. (2012). Mouth dissolving film: A review. *International Journal for Pharmaceutical Research Scholars*, 1, 154–163.
15. Siddiqui, N., Garg, G., & Sharma, P. (2011). A short review on “A novel approach in oral fast dissolving drug delivery system and their patents”. *Advances in Biological Research*, 5, 291–303.
16. Dixit, R., & Puthli, S. P. (2009). Oral strip technology: Overview and future potential. *Journal of Controlled Release*, 139, 94–107.
17. Mahajan, A., Chhabra, N., & Aggarwal, G. (2011). Formulation and characterization of fast dissolving buccal films: A review. *Scholars Research Library*, 3, 152–165.
18. Rathi, V., Senthil, V., Kammili, L., & Hans, R. (2011). A brief review on oral film technology. *International Journal of Research in Ayurveda and Pharmacy*, 2, 1138–1147.
19. Bhyan, B., Jangra, S., Kaur, M., & Singh, H. (2011). Orally fast dissolving films: Innovations in formulation and technology. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, 9, 50–57.
20. Madhulika, G. S. S. V., & Kuber, B. R. (2019). A review on natural and synthetic polymers employed in the formulation of oral disintegrating tablets. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 9(2-s), 652–658.
21. Rakesh, P., & Nisha, G. (2011). Superdisintegrants in the development of orally disintegrating tablets – A review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Research*, 2(11), 2767–2780.
22. Sparsh, G., Rakesh, R. M., & Vashali, G. (2015). Novel study in fast dissolving drug delivery system: A review. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biological Research*, 3(1), 93–107.
23. Jyoti, V., Prajapati, S. K., & Irchhiaya, R. (2017). An overview on superdisintegrants: A review. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 4(9), 252–260.
24. Parind, M. D., Celin, V. L., & Paul, S. H. (2015). Review of disintegrants and the disintegration phenomena. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 1–11.
25. Rajvi, Y., Bhadoriya, A., & Patani, P. (2022). Polymers use in mouth dissolving formulation: A review article. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 13(5), 2579–2586.
26. Priyanka, N., Chauhan, I., & Yasir, M. (2011). Insights into polymers: Film formers in mouth dissolving films. *Drug Invention Today*, 3, 280–289.
27. Kiyose, M., Yamamoto, E., Yamane, C., Midorikawa, T., & Takahashi, T. Structure and properties of low-substituted hydroxypropyl cellulose films and fibers regenerated from aqueous sodium hydroxide solution.
28. Shirsand, S. B., Para, M. S., Ramani, R. G., Swamy, P. V., Nagendra Kumar, D., & Rampure, M. V. (2010). Novel co-processed superdisintegrants in the design of fast dissolving tablets. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Technology and Research*, 2(1), 222–227.
29. Sachdeva, S., Singh, H., & Singh, J. (2024). Enhancing dissolution and bioavailability: A review on co-processed superdisintegrants in pharmaceutical formulations. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 14(8).

30. Hannan, P., Khan, J. A., Khan, A., & Safiullah, S. (2016). Oral dispersible system: A new approach in drug delivery system. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 78(2). <https://doi.org/10.4103/0250-474X.180244>
31. Panda, B., Dey, N. S., & Rao, M. E. B. (2012). Development of innovative orally fast disintegrating film dosage forms: A review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 5, 1666–1674.
32. Prodduturi, S., Manek, R., Kolling, W., Stodghill, S., & Repka, M. (2005). Solid-state stability and characterization of hot-melt extruded poly(ethylene oxide) films. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 94, 2232–2245.
33. Janssens, S., Armas, H. N., Remon, J. P., & Van den Mooter, G. (2007). The use of a new hydrophilic polymer, Kollicoat IR®, in the formulation of solid dispersions of itraconazole. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 30, 288–294.
34. Teckoe, J., Labriola, A., Hansell, J., & Farrell, T. (2012). Stability study of PEG free, PVA based film coating system. *AAPS*, 1–4.
35. Haff, F., Sanner, A., & Straub, F. (1985). Polymers of N-vinyl pyrrolidone: Synthesis, characterization and uses. *Polymer Journal*, 17, 143–152.
36. Sapkal, N., Kilor, V. A., Daud, A. S., & Bonde, M. N. (2011). Development of fast dissolving oral thin films of ambroxol hydrochloride: Effect of formulation variables. *Journal of Advanced Pharmaceutical Research*, 2, 102–109.
37. Desai, P. M., Liew, C. V., & Heng, P. W. S. (2016). Review of disintegrants and the disintegration phenomena. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 105, 2545–2555.
38. Quodbach, J., Moussavi, A., Tammer, R., Frahm, J., & Kleinebudde, P. (2014). Tablet disintegration studied by high-resolution real-time magnetic resonance imaging. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 103(1), 249–255.
39. Augsburger, L. L., Brzezczko, A. W., Shah, U., & Hahm, H. A. (2007). Super disintegrants – characterization and function. In J. Swarbrick (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of pharmaceutical technology* (3rd ed., pp. 3553–3567). Informa Healthcare USA, Inc.
40. Colombo, P., Conte, U., Caramella, C., Geddo, M., & La Manna, A. (1984). Disintegrating force as a new formulation parameter. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 73(5), 701–705.